

Burntwood-Langenkamp Project, Mercer County (40.50103, -84.59570)

Since construction in 2022, the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project's main nutrient benefit has been filtering actively pumped and passive inflows occurring at high flows from Burntwood Creek. A design modification adding a sump pit (hole in front of the pump to allow greater water volumes) was made in 2024 to increase flow volume and succeeded in more than doubling the inflow as compared to 2023. The Project's active management and pump-driven system moderated potential drought impacts in 2024, and the Project filtered 8.9 lbs phosphorus per acre, in addition to its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source contributing 0.6 lbs phosphorus per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this flow-through Project is actively managed. The Project has 27 acres of restored wetland. Water enters from Burntwood Creek via a pump (managed by ODNR staff) or via the inflow notch when water reaches a certain threshold. The water resides in a pool or flows through a sinuous path between various pools before reaching the outflow into Coldwater Creek, at which there is a water level control structure that can be manually adjusted. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which Burntwood Creek flow reaches 27 cubic feet per second, as this is when researchers estimate the creek flows through the inflow notch.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar actively managed flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Digging of sump to allow water to be pumped into the wetland for longer durations doubled the total inflow of water treated by the Project.
- Modifications to create more shallow, slow-flow habitat with longer residence time would increase the capacity of the wetland to retain nutrients through vegetation by expanding the available area for wetland plants to establish.
- Active hydrologic management can moderate potential drought impacts by ensuring large hydrologic events are captured and held. Pump-driven systems can also perform this function, mechanically facilitating water/nutrient inputs even when water levels in the creek are below the threshold for the inflow notch.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.